

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LIBRARIANSHIP: POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақоламизда ахборот-кутубхоначилик фаолиятидаги хизматлар самарадорлигини оширишда сунъий интеллект технологияларидан фойдаланишнинг долзарб масалалари таҳлилий тадқиқ қилинган.

Калим сўзлар: сунъий интеллект, рақамли трансформация, ахборот-ресурс маркази.

Аннотация. В данной статье аналитически исследуются актуальные вопросы использования технологий искусственного интеллекта в повышении эффективности услуг в информационно-библиотечной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, цифровая трансформация, информационно-ресурсный центр.

Abstract. In this article, current issues of the use of artificial intelligence technologies in improving the efficiency of services in information-library activities are analytically researched.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, digital transformation, information resource center.

In the context of digital transformation and intensive technological development in the modern world, areas traditionally considered to be the domain of the human factor are increasingly faced with the possibility of introducing artificial intelligence (AI). Librarianship is no exception, and in recent years, the introduction of AI in this area has been actively discussed by specialists and researchers.

The use of artificial intelligence in librarianship opens up new horizons of possibilities, from the automation and optimization of traditional library processes to the personalization of services for users. However, with new possibilities come new questions. How does artificial intelligence affect the work of libraries? What benefits and risks does it pose for the library community and users? What strategies should be adopted to make the most of AI in libraries?

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a broad field of science and technology that focuses on the creation and development of machines and software systems that can perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence. This includes, but is not limited to, functions such as speech recognition, learning, planning, problem-solving, perception, natural language processing, and the ability to manipulate and move objects.

An important aspect of AI is the ability to learn and adapt. This means that machines and AI-based programs do not simply follow pre-set instructions, but can learn from new data, experience, and feedback, changing their behavior and improving their performance in the process.

Technically, AI can be divided into two categories: narrow (or weak) AI and general (or strong) AI. Narrow AI is specialized in performing a specific task, such as speech recognition or recommender systems. General AI, on the other hand, has the ability to perform any task that a human can perform, and currently remains in the realm of academic research and science fiction.

The relevance of using AI in librarianship

The relevance of using artificial intelligence (AI) in librarianship is determined by several key factors:

1. **Technological advancement:** Modern information society technologies are becoming increasingly complex and interconnected. This creates the preconditions for the active use of AI in various fields, including librarianship.

2. **Efficiency and automation:** Artificial intelligence can significantly improve efficiency and automate many processes related to library operations, from catalog management to interactive interaction with users.

3. **Personalization of services:** With the help of AI, it is possible to offer personalized recommendations based on the user’s preferences and interests, which will increase user satisfaction and loyalty.

4. **Analytics and forecasting:** AI can be used to analyze user behavior and predict their needs, which allows libraries to respond faster and more accurately to changing trends and preferences.

5. **Social inclusion:** AI can help libraries become more accessible to people with disabilities by providing adaptive and inclusive services.

AI Applications with a Focus on Librarianship

Artificial intelligence is used in a variety of industries, including healthcare, finance, education, retail, transportation, and many more. It helps improve efficiency, speed up processes, provide new capabilities for analytics and predictions, and enable more personalized and inclusive services.

In the context of librarianship, AI can be applied in several key areas:

1. **Operational automation:** AI can automate many routine tasks such as cataloguing and classifying materials, managing inventory, handling user queries, etc.

2. **Service personalization:** AI-powered systems can analyze user behavior and preferences to provide personalized recommendations of books, research articles, and other resources.

3. **Interactive customer service:** AI can be used to create chatbots and virtual assistants that can interact with users, answer their questions, help navigate library resources, and provide other services.

4. **Analytics and forecasting:** AI can be used to collect and analyze data on library usage patterns, which helps predict future trends, improve resource planning, and offer more efficient services.

The use of artificial intelligence in libraries is already bringing significant changes to familiar processes. Let's look at some specific examples of the use of AI in the library environment:

1. **Chatbots and virtual assistants:** For example, the San Francisco Library uses a virtual assistant built using AI to help users navigate library services, answer questions, and provide reading recommendations.

2. **Recommender systems:** The Cornell University Library has developed an AI-powered recommender system that suggests scholarly articles, books, and other materials to users based on their search and reading history.

3. **Classification and cataloguing:** Some libraries use AI to automatically classify and catalog new materials, which reduces the time spent on these processes and reduces the possibility of errors.

4. **Digitization and text recognition:** The British Library uses AI in the process of digitizing historical documents. AI helps recognize and transcribe texts, which speeds up the digitization process and makes these materials easier to access.

These examples show that artificial intelligence is already being implemented in librarianship and offers important opportunities to improve library operations and meet user needs [1].

The implementation of artificial intelligence, despite all its benefits, is also associated with a number of issues and challenges. Here are some of them:

1. **Security and privacy issues:** Artificial intelligence, like any technology related to data processing, creates security and privacy risks. This is especially important in the context of libraries, which process users' personal data and must ensure their privacy.

2. **Legal issues:** The use of AI may give rise to new legal issues, such as liability for errors made by AI-based systems or for violations of data processing and storage rules.

3. **Personnel requirements:** The implementation of AI requires employees with the appropriate skills and knowledge. Libraries need to train their staff to work with new technologies, which may require additional resources.

4. **Budget constraints:** Implementing AI can be expensive, especially for smaller libraries with limited budgets.

5. **Bias and bias:** Artificial intelligence can reproduce and amplify existing biases and inequalities if it is trained on biased data.

6. **Accessibility issues:** While AI can improve the accessibility of library services for some users, it can also create barriers for others, especially those who lack the necessary technology skills or have limited access to technology.

In this regard, the introduction of AI in librarianship must be carefully planned and regularly monitored to ensure security, privacy, fairness and accessibility of services for all users [2].

The prospects for the use of artificial intelligence in librarianship are broad and promising. They promise to bring qualitative changes in various aspects of library work and services:

1. **Improved service quality:** AI can significantly improve the quality of library services by making them more personalized, convenient, and efficient. For example, AI can be used to offer users personalized recommendations based on their preferences and reading history, increasing their satisfaction with the library experience.

2. **New user experiences:** AI can open up new opportunities for library users, such as virtual assistants to help them find information, chatbots to answer questions, and even machine learning algorithms to analyze and visualize data.

3. **Optimization of resources:** AI can help libraries optimize the use of their resources by predicting user needs and adapting their services accordingly.

4. **Improved accessibility:** AI can make library services more accessible to people with disabilities, for example through speech recognition and speech synthesis technologies.

5. **Developing digital collections:** AI can play a key role in developing digital collections in libraries by accelerating the digitalization process, improving search and access to materials, and helping to discover new connections and patterns in data.

6. **Enhancing research:** The use of artificial intelligence can enhance research by helping users find, analyze, and interpret information [3].

Thus, the prospects for using AI in librarianship are promising and can lead to significant improvements in service quality and user satisfaction. However, this requires careful planning, adequate funding, continuous staff training, and strict adherence to ethical and legal standards.

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